

FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF THE CARBON/EPOXY AND THE CARBON/PEEK COMPOSITES SUBJECTED TO LOW-ENERGY IMPACT

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SUMMARY: Fatigue behaviors of carbon fiber reinforced thermosetting and thermoplastic composites with and without subjecting low-energy impact were investigated. The [0/45/90/-45]_{2S} T300/976 carbon/epoxy and AS-4/PEEK laminates were used in this study. The impact response of these two laminates shows a linear force-deformation relationship in the initial penetration impact loading, which implies an elastic behavior of these two composites; the following zigzag peaks indicate fracture initiation and arrest. The fatigue tests were performed at various stress levels under tension-tension loadings with a fatigue frequency of 3 and stress ratio of 0.1. The median rank method and Weibull distribution were applied to predict the fatigue probabilities of the specimen under static and fatigue tests. The S-N curves for the undamaged and low-energy impact damaged laminates are compared.

KEYWORDS: low-energy impact, fatigue behavior, T300/976 carbon/epoxy, AS-4/PEEK, Weibull distribution, S-N curve

INTRODUCTION

Although fiber reinforced composite shows many remarkable features such as lower specific strength and modulus, better corrosion resistance, and precise tailoring, the inherent anisotropic property of fiber reinforced composites results in much more complicated fracture mode than that of the conventional materials. During the past two decades, carbon/epoxy composites have been adopted in many applications, and numerous studies on the fatigue properties of the laminates have been reported[1,5]. On the other hand, carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite such as Gr/PEEK laminate is a relatively new material; only a few studies were performed on the topic of fatigue behavior for Gr/PEEK laminates[6-8]. Besides fatigue behavior, impact behavior is also a very important property for composites in engineering applications[9]. On the applications of composites in transportation vehicles, the damages can be introduced during maintenance such as dropped tool and during service such as debris rebound; all these damages result in reduction of performance. However, very few articles were published to investigate the effects of the combined loading, fatigue and impact, on the performance of the Gr/epoxy and Gr/PEEK composites. The purposes of this work are to study the fatigue behavior of the low-energy impacted composites and to compare the performance of the quasi-isotropic thermosetting (Gr/epoxy) and thermoplastic (Gr/PEEK) composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

P3051F Gr/epoxy and AS-4/PEEK prepregs were supplied by Toray in Japan and Imperial Chemical Industry (I.C.I.) in U.K., respectively. The Gr/epoxy and Gr/PEEK laminates were fabricated in autoclave and hot press, respectively. Specimens were cut from fabricated panels through a water-cooled diamond table saw. The dimensions of the test coupons are 227mm x 19.1 mm x 2mm with a gage length of 127 mm. Non-tapered glass/epoxy end tabs with dimensions of 50 mm x 19.1 mm x 1.6 mm were used.

The cross-section area of the test specimens for penetration impact was 100 mm x 100 mm. The impact procedure was conducted using a steel impactor of cylindrical shape with a hemispherical nose 19.0 mm in diameter and 17.01 kg in weight. The diameter of the support ring is 76 mm.

Low-velocity impact tests were conducted using a Dynatup/GRC drop weight impact tester. The specimens were firmly fixed between flat circular rings with a support ring 18 mm in diameter. The impact machine is equipped with a hemispherical nose 12.7 mm in diameter and a rebound apparatus to prevent multiple impacts. Various energies for low-energy impact tests were employed by changing the hammer height.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

The two-parameter Weibull distribution function, which is shown in Eq. (1), was adopted to analyze strength, residual strength after impact, and fatigue life.

$$R_i (X_i) = 1 - \exp \left[- \left(\frac{X_i}{X_o} \right)^{\alpha_s} \right] \quad (1)$$

The median rank is employed in Eq. (2) for failure probability, $R(X_i)$ at X_i , $1 < i < m$,

$$R (X_i) = \frac{i - 0.3}{m + 0.4} \quad (2)$$

where X_i denotes the test strength of fatigue life of the i^{th} specimen.

Based upon the data of fatigue cycles to failure under various stress levels, the S-N curves were plotted using linear regression method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 1a and 1b show the relationship among force, deformation, and energy during penetration impact loading for both Gr/epoxy and Gr/PEEK laminates, respectively. Although the differences in energies required to penetrate these two laminates are not obvious, the responses during impact loading of these two composites are different. A linear relation between force and deformation for these two laminates can be observed during the initial penetration process, which implies an elastic behavior of the composites. After the linear region, a force relaxation which indicates the formation of a fracture surface is detected for

Gr/epoxy laminates only. On the other hand, no obvious peak can be detected before reaching the peak load for Gr/PEEK laminates. As compared the deformation at which the peak load is reached of these two laminates, Gr/PEEK composites show greater deformation than Gr/epoxy composites, which implies better damage tolerance of the Gr/PEEK laminates. Further verification can be made by comparing the response of the composites after peak load; a sharp drop in force is detected, which indicates the formation of a large fracture surface in Gr/epoxy composites. However, only slightly reduction in force can be observed for Gr/PEEK laminates, which implies less force relaxation and fracture surface formation. The total energy to penetrate the laminate is denoted as E_i .

Figure 2 shows the strengths of the unimpacted specimens and the impact-damaged specimens loaded under various impact energies. The strength is reduced with increasing impact energy for both composites. Moreover, the rate of decrease in tensile strength for Gr/PEEK is higher than that of the Gr/epoxy laminates. After impact loading, a wider distribution in tensile strength is also detected.

The failure probabilities of the unimpacted and the 25% E_i impacted Gr/epoxy laminates were compared in Figure 3a; a slight difference in failure probability can be observed; and the impact damage results in a broader distribution in strength is also detected. However, nearly no difference in failure probability predicted by Weibull function can be observed for Gr/PEEK laminates (Figure 3b), although some experimental data have a significant deviation from theoretical prediction.

Figure 4a shows the S-N curves of unimpacted and impacted Gr/epoxy composites. A linear stress-fatigue life relationship is obtained. The shift of the curve implies that low-energy impact results in lower fatigue life, however, no significant variation in slope is observed, which indicates both composites (unimpacted and impacted) having similar fatigue sensitivity. Figure 4b shows the S-N curves of the unimpacted and 25% E_i impacted Gr/PEEK composites, and it reveals that low-energy impact loading results in the reduction of fatigue life for Gr/PEEK composites. A linear S-N curves were obtained using linear regression analysis. In our previous study, the Gr/PEEK composite shows two-segment S-N curves[6]; the difference between these two results may be due to different testing conditions and analytical methods. Furthermore, it is also observed that fatigue life distribution becomes less spread at lower stress level when the Gr/PEEK composites were subjected to a low-energy impact.

CONCLUSIONS

Penetration impact loadings were applied to Gr/epoxy and Gr/PEEK laminates; Gr/epoxy shows a brittle fracture behavior, whereas Gr/PEEK shows a plastic fracture mode. The tensile strength reduces with increasing impact energy for both Gr/epoxy and Gr/PEEK laminates. A good correlation between experimental data and theoretical analysis for failure prediction in tensile strength is achieved. The data of fatigue life to failure indicate that the fatigue life is reduced when the specimens were subjected to a low-energy impact, and the distribution becomes less spread for both Gr/epoxy and Gr/PEEK composites.

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Fig. 1: Relationship among deformation, force, and energy during penetration impact loadings for (a) Gr/epoxy and (b) Gr/PEEK laminates

2(a)

2(b)

Fig. 2: Residual strength of the specimens after being subjected to various impact energies for (a) Gr/epoxy and (b) Gr/PEEEK laminates

3(a)

3(b)

Fig. 3: Weibull distribution of the composites without and with subjected to 25% E_i impact loading for (a) Gr/epoxy and (b) Gr/PEEK laminates

